

Calibration of material models applied to impact mechanics using a new statistical approach

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Real life projects suitability

Outline

- 1 Meta-models and GSA
- 2 Bayesian Calibration
- 3 Real application to complex material modeling

1. Meta-models and GSA

Meta-models structure

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- Non-parametric meta-model, composed of **Radial Basis Functions** (RBF Kernel) → Natural extension to high dimensions
- Scatter data approximation: Model sampled at N_s input points
- Output $Y_n \rightarrow$ linear combination $Y(X_n) \approx \sum_{k=1}^{N_k} \beta_k h_k(X_n)$
- Error estimation: $Err = \frac{\|Y(X_{ev}) - H(X_{ev})\beta\|}{N_{sev} \|H(X_{ev})\beta\|}$

Global Sensitivity Analysis (GSA)

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- Total effects measure contribution of the individual effect and its interactions with other parameters: $ST_i = \frac{E_{x_{-i}}(V_{x_{-i}}(Y|X_{-i}))}{V(Y)}$

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- Thousands of simulations could be needed...**meta-models are essential**

2. Bayesian calibration

Theoretics of Bayesian calibration

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- Likelihood function → two **Gaussian processes** emulating η and δ
- Prior pdfs → normal, uniform, etc.

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- Summarizing:

3. Real application to complex material modeling

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- $N_s = 200$ (Maximin LHS) considered for each speed point to get reliable meta-models

GSA analysis

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- Very stable sensitivity indices for the range → Filtering **A**, **B** and **C** parameters is reliable

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- 1 Variable input $X \rightarrow$ impact speed
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- Simulated input \rightarrow 200 simulations over the speed range considering Maximin LHS variation (possible to generate quick data collection using meta-models)

Model calibration

- A priori pdfs for material parameters as $N \sim (\mu, 1)$, with μ obtained from [Samantaray et al., 2009]
- A priori pdfs for hyperparameters $\sigma_\delta \sim \Gamma(2, 0.01)$ and $v_\delta \sim U(0, 1)$ (tentative), while error variance $\sigma_{err} \sim \Gamma(1, 0.1)$

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- *CaliCo* package [Carmassi et al., 2018] used in R for this procedure

Calibration results

- Initial model with first guesses (not calibrated)

Calibration results

- Calibrated model

Calibration results

- Calibrated parameters and uncertainty

Summary

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